

UDK: 72 (075)

**SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE CREATION OF
SMALL GARDENS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE CLIMATE OF
UZBEKISTAN**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7848057>

Imamov Mukhiddin Rustamovich

Senior Lecturer of the Department of "Theory and History of Architecture"

Samarkand State university of Architecture and Construction, Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

Telephone: +99899 043-13-47 e-mail: muhiddinimomov38@gmail.com

Akhtam Sindarovich Uralov

*arch.F., d., professor Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Аннотация.

Мақолада кичик боғларни яратиш бўйича ишлаб чиқилган меъморий дастур, кичик боғларнинг атрибутлари ва семантикаси, кичик боғларни яратишнинг меъморий дастури, кичик боғларда қўлланиладиган ландшафт композициялари бўйича тавсиялар, сув дунёси ва мўъжаз меъмор-ий шакллар бўйича тавсиялар, амалий лойиҳавий таклифлар келтирилган.

Аннотация.

В статье представлены разработанная архитектурная программа создания малых садов, атрибуты и семантика малых садов, архитектурная программа создания малых садов, рекомендации по ландшафтным композициям, используемым в малых садах, рекомендации по водному миру и прекрасным архитектурным формам, а также практические предложения по дизайну.

Keywords.

Small gardens, architectural program, water world and wonderful architectural forms, topiary gardens, roof gardens, windows, umbrella roofs, porches, windows, seats.

Enter. In the scientific researches of world scientists dedicated to garden time, compositional methods of forming modern small gardens, innovations in the field are noted. The creation of new artistic forms of small gardens, the use of new materials and modern technologies, the formation of the scientific and theoretical bases of the development of small gardens in cities has become of urgent importance. However, in the practice of Uzbekistan, the study of the innovations of

the foundations of the formation of small gardens and their use is being carried out slowly.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan published the 222 DECA-bridewe 2010 DECs 2010 and the decision of 2011 to strengthen the material and technical base of cultural and recreational fields and approve the activities of the activities of their activities is largely in the country and was aimed at developing large gardens. However, designing small gardens and proposals for our daily needs of the architectural landscape until this time is the world practice of the Central Asian republics of the subjects of landscapes. and it is clear that it will be behind the science. Therefore, the creation of the architectural program in the Republican Association of Smiz Development of Small Parks has the right to call one of the topical problems that comes from the needs of our life.

The main part. Small gardens are the main object of the landscape design. The small garden is located in the territory of landscape design using landscape design, in the territory of the courtyards and recreational buildings, and in terms of recreational facilities, limited gardens in terms of registry. The territory of small gardens can usually be 0.2 hectares from 0.2 hectares to 1-2 hectares, in some cases up to 5 hectares. If their area is up to 20 sail, they are called gold orchards. The small bond is usually included in the areas of housing, offices, hotel complexes, super-grades, sanatoriums, preschools, preschools, preschools, and preschools, schools, preschools and other institutions. [1]

Small gardens can also be located in the territories of residential areas. Such a garden is usually the garden of the group of housing houses, the microchronic district, courtyard garden, the cottages, cottages, are the courtyards and other gardeners of the cottages. The small gardens have a compact location content and can also be included in the compact parks, which are also located in different industries in the same industrial buildings. The roofing gardens and yard gardens are also important views of small gardens.[5]

Modern typology of small gardens is very rich, meaningful, and their number is growing day by day. In addition to the development of historical types of small gardens, their composition is composed of a unique bouquet of combined small gardens. Modern forms of small gardens are yard gardens of winter gardens, roofing gardens and public buildings, parking of monophunction, flowering flowers, melons), dry landlines (melons), dry landlines (melons) an aliparium, rocaries, rocky hills). And this classification is not a hardened today, it is developing. [4]

Studies aimed at creating an architectural program of small gardens should begin with the Concept of the Chartamental topic, which is typical of the Gardens of Islamic Islamic Thus, the content of our architectural program, which is offered to create a traditional pledbar is a small park, consists of the following:

- The architectural solution of the architecture is regularly composition "Chartbag", where the right paths and alleys, ditches, channels, basins, pools, and the availability should be important;

- It was in accordance with the purpose of the garden, as possible, and the beauty of the garden is high and facing the south as possible;

- The water in small garden ditches is not under sunlight, but the shadow of the shadow. It is advisable to be a pool in the garden, the sowing of shady path trees that do not fall into it. Then the poem's face is closed with shadows, the water is clean, a healthy click is formed;

- Flowering trees planted in the garden is formed from large varieties of flowers, formed a former green environment, contrast to the previous Closed green environment. After the atmosphere of flowers, green ornamental trees are always planted. When the flowering bushes of the garden climb is gonna get better. When the last grass of the garden is sown from any fruit trees, they protect the garden from the winds and gives beautiful fruits. It is advisable for the planting of simple analogues between the fruit trees.

- The center of the small garden has lifted to the garden, soakunak space, so that the Khossios of the whole garden can be seen. It is better to operate the governor rose and myine, and the flavoring flowerbeds to work around the garden. And this garden should be thicker, where those who walk are blinded by their eyesops to beautiful landscapes around;

- National pillows, designed to sit or restrained in the garden, are the carpets, "barking" or "skylish fluke" or the most important of them, the "Paradise ditches" are expident. When they are collected from gravel on the ditch or channel, the heat of water gives more pleasure;

- The composition of the garden should be considered important components of the garden in the garden (Zark, Fountain, Pond, Chapoya, Corridor, Corridor, Ariq) garden, and in harmony according to its tarhi. This architectural integrity, that is, the harmony between garden and its buildings or gardens must become the main principle of gardening design. To do this, the geometry of the garden, all elements and buildings is required to be based on the law of regular, secting symmetrylike, similar, regular, other symmetry.

In the small garden, these laws, that is, the principles, must take the leading position. These key architectural principles also need to be included in the main area of ornamental and fruit trees, tilly artificial forms. Only then will this Ki-Chic will be the opportunity to create not only Uzbek but also the hearts of others. [3]

The garden semantics is a common architectural-art idea of this small garden, its elements, poles, location and mutual complexity of green plants. [2]

The formation of the architectural-planned method of the park is carried out by dividing its territory to fukal zones and determining these zones in line with these zones. The main tasks of the small garden formation includes the park area from the surrounding device, organize the following ways to arrange and organize the rest of the garden, the placement of the holidays, the heads and slanderers, etc. These main tasks must be considered carefully in developing a small garden planned solution. The most complex issue is to create and form an artistic architectural-landlose image of a small garden. [1]

The main facilities of the small garden are polemas, umbrellas, roofs, woolish, seats, etc.; Water devices, wide, waterfall, shalolas, decorative bases; Decorative statues and others.

Plants recommended in the formation of small gardens in the climate of Uzbekistan includes Rakht (Glidichia, Slydora, Jiya, Saxis, Whin Aquatics, Vir-Gin, Elder, Sarv, Sarv, Swamp Portvites); from the bushes (amorfas, sand-acunction, ligustrum, Freestyle, Totim, Dry, Na'matak); Lianes (In Uzbekistan, the city of Amur, Purchal Devichi Vinograd, Chinese Glitstina, Jim-Omin Capinchi, Jim-Omin Coppius, Jim-Omost Capinchi, Jim-Omost Capinch, Clothes, Places, Tokom, and others); From the flowers (Always Spring, Hanjari, Cook, Malbar, Darkhari mak, Mount Savdari, and a simple Savri, Sunsan, Sorhaik, yellow, Yellow Lola, Nastarin, Baghdadi, Cuzgo, Guli, Shabs and Dumon, Chaman Agruz and Gultoquiaz ("Gil-AM" appeared from Plants are planted in timy, lights.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

- 1.Уралов А.С., Садикова С.Н. Ўрта Осиё анъанавий “Чорбоғ” услуби ва замонавий боғ-парк санъати. - Т.,2012.
- 2.Ожегов С.С., Уралов А.С., Рахимов К.Ж. Ландшафт архитектураси ва дизайни. – Самарканд, 2003.
- 3.Приходько П.И. Ландшафтная композиция малого сада.-Киев, 1976.

4. Rustamovich, I. M. (2023). Modern trends and typology of designing small gardens. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(2), 52-55.

5. Rustamovich, I. M. (2023). Modern classification system and typology of small gardens. *JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE*, 2(2), 56-59.

6. Bakhridinovna, K. K., & Rustamovich, I. M. (2021). Architectural Ceramics of Ancient Samarkand. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 3(7), 7-10. <https://doi.org/10.31149/ijot.v3i7.2040>

7. Mukhiddin Imomov Rustamovich, & Jasur Berdikulov Begimovich. (2020). Principles of landscape architecture and design of small gardens of modern hospitals in the climate of Uzbekistan. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 2(12), 7-9. <https://doi.org/10.31149/ijot.v2i12.983>

8. Имомов, М. Р. (2023). ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ШАРОИТИДА КИЧИК БОҒЛАРДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛАДИГАН СУВ ДУНЁСИ ВА МЎЖАЗ МЕЪМОРИЙ ШАКЛЛАР БЎЙИЧА ТАВСИЯЛАР. *АРХИТЕКТУРА, МУHANDISLIK VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR JURNALI*, 2(1), 144-148.

9. Имомов, М. (2020). РАЗРЕШЕНИЕ ЛАНДШАФТНЫХ БОЛЬНИЦ И НЕБОЛЬШИХ ПАРКОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ НЕОПРЕДЕЛЕННОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ, ПРИНЦИПЫ ИХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ. *Электронный сетевой политематический журнал "Научные труды кубгту"*, (8), 827-831.

10. Имомов, М. Р., Каримов, У. Н., Нарзиева, К. Қ., & Санакулова, М. Ш. (2018). РЕШЕНИЕ ОЗЕЛЕНЕНИЯ МЕСТ ОБЩЕГО ПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ И ИХ СОСТАВНЫЕ ЧАСТИ. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (5-7), 119-123.

11. Нарзиева, К. К., & Имомов, М. Р. (2018). ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ АРХИТЕКТУРНЫЕ СТРОЕНИЯ СТРАН БЛИЖНЕГО И СРЕДНЕГО ВОСТОКА. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (5-7), 124-128.

7. Elmuradovna, J. E. (2021). The Architecture of Karshi Castle, The Establishment, The Past and the Present. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 247-252.

8. Elmuradovna, J. E. (2021). Bukhara Registan: Past And Present. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 25(1), 160-166.

9. Jurayeva, E. E. (2023). ARCHITECTURE OF TASHKENT REGISTON SQUARE. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(1), 190-203.

10. Elmuradovna, J. E. (2023). TARIXIY SHAHARLARDAGI CHETEL MAYDONLARINING ARXITEKTURASINI TAHLIL QILISH. ARXITEKTURA, MUHANDISLIK VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR JURNALI, 2(1), 20-26.

11. Elmuradovna, J. E. (2023). Scientific Recommendations on Restoration of the Historical Appearance of Anti-Register Not Preserved. Telematique, 22(01), 275-281.

12. Elmuradovna, J. E. (2023). TANIQLI ARXITEKTORLAR IJODINI O'RGANISH. ARXITEKTURA, MUHANDISLIK VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR JURNALI, 2(3), 117-133.

13. Elmuradovna, J. E. (2023). Historical City Centers and their Significance. JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING, MECHANICS AND MODERN ARCHITECTURE, 2(3), 28-32.

14. Juraev, O. J., & Sh, K. L. (2021). DETERMINATION OF SORPTION ABILITY OF ACETATE CELLULOSE MEMBRANE AND POLYMER ADDITIVES. Journal of Advanced Scientific Research (ISSN: 0976-9595), 1(1).

15. Максимчук, О. В., Якубов, К. А., Жураев, О. Ж., Борисова, Н. И., Чижо, Л. Н., Антонян, О. Н., & 15. Соловьева, А. С. (2020). Экономика строительства и эксплуатации систем водоснабжения и водоотведения: умные технологии и решения.